

25 **The evolutionary origin of visual and somatosensory representation in the**
26 **vertebrate pallium**

27 Shreyas M Suryanarayana¹, Juan Pérez-Fernández¹, Brita Robertson¹ and Sten Grillner^{1,2 *}
28
29
30
31
32

33 **Affiliations:**

34 ¹ Department of Neuroscience, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden
35

36 *Correspondence to: sten.grillner@ki.se
37
38
39
40

41 *Amniotes, such as mammals and reptiles have vision and other senses represented in pallium,*
42 *whereas anamniotes like amphibians, fish and cyclostomes (including lamprey) that diverged*
43 *much earlier, were historically thought to process predominantly or even exclusively*
44 *olfactory information in pallium. Here, we show here that there is a separate visual area with*
45 *retinotopic representation and that somatosensory information from the head and trunk is*
46 *represented in an adjacent area in the lamprey pallial cortex (lateral pallium). These cortical*
47 *sensory areas flank a non-primary-sensory motor area. Both vision and somatosensation are*
48 *relayed via the thalamus. These findings suggest that the basic sensorimotor representation of*
49 *the mammalian neocortex, as well as the sensory thalamocortical relay had already evolved*
50 *in the last common ancestor of cyclostomes and gnathostomes around 560 million years ago.*

51
52 The lamprey represents the oldest group of extant vertebrates¹. It is an eel-like creature with a
53 well-developed vision that lives a predatory parasitic life^{2,3}. Here, we investigate the sensory
54 representation (visual and somatosensory) in the lateral pallium (LPal; cortex) of lamprey,
55 and to what degree it resembles that of mammals. The mammalian neocortex is organised into
56 distinct sensory areas, including retinotopic visual and somatotopic somatosensory areas, as
57 well as motor areas. This has been thought to be unique and an evolutionarily recent
58 innovation in mammals⁴⁻⁷. The primary visual area in mammals receives input from the
59 retina, relayed via the lateral geniculate nucleus. In addition, visual information from the
60 superior colliculus is relayed via thalamus to neocortex^{8,9}. Somatosensory information is
61 mediated through the lemniscal input to cortical somatosensory areas via the ventral posterior
62 nucleus of thalamus¹⁰⁻¹².

63
64 In non-mammalian amniotes (reptiles and birds), pallium receives visual, somatosensory and
65 auditory inputs relayed via thalamus^{5,6}. In turtles, the three-layered dorsal cortex has a visual
66 representation, however, reported not to be organised in a retinotopic fashion¹³. Much less is
67 known about the somatosensory organisation in the reptilian dorsal cortex¹⁴. In birds, visual

68 and somatosensory input has been reported to reach the Wulst, a layered pallial structure and
69 in addition, trans-tectal visual input and other sensory modalities also reaches the dorsal
70 ventricular ridge (DVR, a large pallial structure in sauropsids consisting of nuclei) in both
71 avian and non-avian reptiles^{5,15-21}. Across mammals, the neocortical sensory mapping adheres
72 to a common regionalisation and modality specific patterning, and is acknowledged to have
73 been present in the last common ancestor of all extant mammals^{7,18,22}. Only in mammals has a
74 clear retinotopic and somatotopic representation been established in the neocortex.

75

76 In anamniotes (amphibians, jawed fishes and cyclostomes), the information is less precise,
77 and pallium has been thought to process predominantly olfactory inputs^{23,24,25}. In lamprey, it
78 has recently been demonstrated that the lateral pallium is three-layered and can be considered
79 a homologue region of the mammalian cortex²⁶, and will be referred to as the lamprey cortex
80 below. It contains glutamatergic neurons (around 80%) and GABAergic interneurons (around
81 20%) and its efferent connectivity is similar to that of the mammalian neocortex²⁷. Moreover,
82 eye, orienting, locomotor and oral movements can be elicited from the motor area. We now
83 show that there are indeed separate retinotopic visual and somatotopic somatosensory
84 representation in the lamprey cortex, in addition to the motor area²⁷. In amphibians, there is
85 scant data, other than tracing studies indicating thalamic input to medial pallium²⁸. In
86 elasmobranchs (shark), optic nerve stimulation results in a visual response in the telencephalic
87 central posterior nucleus²⁹, and in teleosts, input from retina reaches thalamus and
88 somatosensory information reaches the related preglomerular complex. Both structures
89 project to pallium but part of the projections is thought to be multimodal³⁰⁻³⁴.

90

91 By using the isolated eye-brain preparation^{35,36}, we demonstrate that in lamprey there is a
92 distinct visual area in cortex with a retinotopic representation. This visual pathway resembles
93 the lateral geniculate relay to the primary visual area in mammals. In addition to the visual
94 area, we show a somatosensory representation from the head (trigeminal sensory nerve) and
95 trunk (dorsal column), and that this sensory input is also mediated via thalamus. We further
96 show that the sensory information is relayed via the sensory trigeminal nucleus and the dorsal
97 column nucleus through the lemniscal pathway. This data is a detailed demonstration of
98 topographic visual and somatosensory representation in any anamniote pallium, suggesting
99 that the basic sensorimotor organisation present in neocortex had evolved already at the dawn
100 of vertebrate evolution, and thereby redefines the evolutionary ancestry of the neocortex.

101

102 **Results:**

103 **A visual area with retinotopy present in the dorsal part of the lateral pallium**

104 To explore whether visual information is represented with any specificity in the lamprey
105 lateral pallium (cortex), we have used an isolated eye-brain preparation in which either the
106 eyes or only the retina remained intact (Figs. 1a and 1h; see Methods). The retina was
107 electrically stimulated in different locations (quadrants, colour-coded) and the response
108 recorded extracellularly (local field potentials, LFPs) in cortex. Each stimulation point, only
109 activated a limited region within the visual area (Figs. 1c-1f, upper traces), and stimulation of
110 other retinal areas had no effect (Figs. 1c-1f, lower traces), but activated instead another
111 visual cortical locus. Within a circumscribed visual area, retinal stimulation in different
112 locations thus resulted in a clear response in only one specific area suggesting a retinotopic
113 organisation (Fig. 1b, bar graphs in Figs. 1c-1f; n=15; onset delay 23 ± 1.3 ms; delay for
114 maximum amplitude 28 ± 2.8 ms). The heatmaps to the right show the retinal regions eliciting
115 maximum response for each recording site in the visual area. The heatmap in Fig. 1g

116 summarises all four recording points and their retinotopic location in relation to each other.
117 We thus conclude that each part of the retina activates a specific and distinct part of the visual
118 area in cortex, demonstrating a retinotopic representation analogous to that seen in the
119 mammalian visual neocortex.

120 The next step was to show that visually processed stimuli also could elicit responses in the
121 visual area. Points expanding rapidly in size (looming stimuli) were presented from a
122 computer screen and resulted in a distinct response in the visual area (Fig. 1i; n=6). Similarly,
123 a transient black screen resulted in an ON and subsequent OFF response (n=8). This
124 demonstrates that visual stimuli indeed are relayed to and represented in the lamprey visual
125 cortex.

126 To investigate whether changes in local excitability in the visual area would affect the
127 response, D-glutamate was microinjected locally in this area, which resulted in an enhanced
128 response (Figs. 1j and 1k; n=3). Similarly, a blockade of the local GABAergic interneuron
129 transmission with injections of gabazine (n=8) resulted in a marked increase of the stimulus-
130 evoked activity. In addition, it resulted in loss of retinotopy (Extended Data Fig. 1) wherein
131 all retinal stimulation points produced a response in any visual cortical recording points. This
132 suggests that inhibitory interneurons provide local inhibition and sharpen the retinotopy.
133 Essentially, there is a separate visual area in the dorsal part of the lateral pallium (cortex)
134 which, maintains a retinotopic organisation of visual inputs.

135 **Characterising visual cortical neurons – membrane properties, morphology and** 136 **responses to optic nerve stimulation**

137 To characterise neurons in the visual cortex and to compare them with their mammalian
138 counterparts, we performed whole-cell recordings from brain slices that included the cortical
139 area, thalamus and the optic chiasm/nerve (Fig. 2a; n=9). Figs. 2f and 2g show the
140 morphology of a recorded visual pallial cell. Note that one of the dendrites of the neuron
141 extends into the medial pallium where thalamic afferents enter (see also Extended Data Fig.
142 2). The optic nerve at the entrance to the chiasm was activated with eight pulses, which
143 resulted in successive excitatory postsynaptic potentials (EPSPs) and action potentials (Fig.
144 2b). The EPSPs evoked by the stimulus train progressively declined in amplitude (Figs. 2b
145 and Fig. 2e, blue trace), and the synapse can thus be characterised as depressing. The stimuli
146 evoked excitation, but also inhibition (Fig. 2c), visible when the membrane potential was held
147 at a depolarised level and the cell therefore spiking. Under these conditions, the net effect was
148 an inhibition of the spike train during the stimulation. As expected, administering gabazine
149 resulted in a prolonged and potentiated response (Fig. 2d). The firing properties of cells
150 recorded in the visual area (Fig. 2h) are similar to those in other areas of cortex²⁶, mostly
151 regular firing on intracellular step depolarisations, with an afterhyperpolarization and a
152 postinhibitory rebound depolarisation (Figs. 2i-2k, Supplementary Table S1a). Thus, visual
153 input relayed via the thalamus excites both excitatory and inhibitory neurons in the visual
154 cortex with the inhibitory neurons aiding in the maintenance of the retinotopy.

155 **Somatosensory input relayed via thalamus targets a distinct cortical region with** 156 **separate representation of trigeminal and dorsal column inputs**

157 To explore if there is also a somatosensory representation, we stimulated the contralateral
158 sensory afferents of the trigeminal nerve (n=7) and the dorsal column (n=9), while recording
159 from different areas in cortex (Figs. 3a-3c). We could show that stimulation of the trigeminal
160 nerve gave rise to activation (Fig. 3b, blue trace; Fig. 3d, delay for onset 9.3 ± 1.4 ms; delay
161 for maximum amplitude 18.5 ± 5.7 ms) in a limited area, while stimulation of the dorsal
162 column gave similar responses but with longer latency (Fig. 3b, pink trace; Fig. 3e, delay for

163 onset 45.5 ± 4.8 ms; delay for maximum amplitude 50.5 ± 7.7 ms) in an adjacent area (Fig.
164 3c, blue and pink dots, respectively). This general somatosensory area is located lateral to the
165 visual area and medial to the motor area. We can thus conclude that somatosensory
166 information from head and body is represented in adjacent areas in the lamprey cortex as in
167 the mammalian neocortex.

168 **Somatosensory information from the dorsal column nucleus is relayed via a lemniscal** 169 **pathway to thalamus and pallium**

170 The dorsal column axons in the spinal cord were known to provide EPSPs in neurons of the
171 dorsal column nuclei (DCN)³⁷. It was, however, unclear whether DCN projects to thalamus.
172 We show now that injections in thalamus retrogradely labelled neurons in the DCN (Fig. 3f,
173 injection site in inset; n=3). Moreover, these retrogradely labelled cells in DCN receive dorsal
174 column input as shown by anterogradely labelled fibers following injection in the dorsal
175 column in the rostral spinal cord (Fig. 3g, injection site in inset; see Fig. 3m for the
176 experimental paradigm). Fig. 3h illustrates the dendrite of a thalamus-projecting DCN cell
177 (magenta) juxtaposed with the dorsal column axon (blue), and when combined with the
178 synaptic marker synaptotagmin (green), synapses are visualised (white arrowheads; n=4).
179 Conversely, injections in the DCN anterogradely labelled fibers terminating in thalamus (Fig.
180 3i, injection site in inset; see Fig. 3n for the experimental paradigm; n=5). Furthermore, to
181 verify that DCN cells actually synapse on thalamocortical cells as in mammals, we show
182 dendrites of a retrogradely labelled thalamocortical cell in close apposition to anterogradely
183 labelled DCN axons as indicated with synaptotagmin (Figs. 3j-3l and 3o; n=3). We further
184 investigated how dorsal column inputs are relayed to thalamus (described below), as depicted
185 in the schematics (Fig. 3p).

186 Somatosensory information had been reported not to reach the thalamic level in lamprey in
187 contrast to jawed vertebrates^{24,25}. Injections of Neurobiotin into the DCN (Fig. 4a, red area
188 and *inset* 4b) were made to anterogradely label their axonal trajectory. The fibers cross at the
189 level of DCN and the posterior rhombencephalic reticular nucleus (PRRN; Figs. 4a and 4g)
190 and are visible as a discrete bundle at the level of the middle rhombencephalic reticular
191 nucleus (MRRN; Figs. 4a and 4f). The axons continue rostrally in a ventral position at the
192 level of trigeminal motor nucleus (Figs. 4a and 4e) and ascend to traverse just caudal to the
193 tectum (Figs. 4a and 4c-4d) and pretectum (Figs. 4a and 4b) as a lemniscal bundle to
194 terminate in thalamus. The major proportion of the projections are to the contralateral
195 thalamus (Fig. 4a). This delineates the somatosensory pathway and shows that also in lamprey
196 there is a projection from DCN directly to thalamus that conveys somatosensory information
197 to pallium, similar to mammals. With regard to the trigeminal input we could show
198 retrogradely labelled neurons in a trigeminal sensory nucleus from injections in the thalamus
199 (Extended Data Fig. 3; n=4). These neurons in the trigeminal sensory nucleus, also referred to
200 as the *nucleus of the radix descendens nervi trigemini*³⁸ received synapses from the trigeminal
201 afferents (Extended Data Fig. 3). Thus, the trigeminal sensory afferents reaches the trigeminal
202 sensory nucleus, which projects to thalamus. The thalamus in turn relays this information to
203 the somatosensory cortex (Extended Data Fig. 3).

204 **Characterising thalamic relay neurons and retinotopic specificity within the thalamus**

205 The thalamic sensory relay to neocortex is a critical part of sensory processing. Retinal
206 afferents are known to have collaterals in the dorsolateral thalamus in lamprey^{39,40,41}. Using
207 slices that contained the optic tract, thalamus and thalamic neurons retrogradely labelled from
208 the visual cortex allowed us to identify thalamocortical neurons and record from them (Fig.
209 5a; n=11). Fig. 5b shows an intracellularly labelled thalamocortical neuron with dendrites
210 extending into the optic tract. In a single optical section (Fig. 5c), the dendrite (blue), the optic

211 nerve fiber (magenta) with the synapse immunostained for synaptotagmin (green, colocalised
212 white) are shown. Recordings from the same neuron were performed, while different
213 locations in the optic tract were stimulated (Figs. 5d-g; n=9). One location produces a large
214 response (Fig. 5d, blue trace), while only a small response occurs with another stimulus
215 location in the optic tract (5d, green trace). If the cell is kept at a depolarised holding potential
216 it fires continuously, and when the optic tract is stimulated there will be a pause suggesting
217 that it is inhibited (Fig. 5e), whereas after gabazine application, blocking GABAergic
218 inhibition, there will instead be a large potentiation (Fig. 5f). In another cell, held at different
219 membrane potentials, the inhibitory effect is shown after intracellular blockade of sodium
220 channels with QX314 (Figs. 5g and 5h). The optic tract evokes facilitatory EPSPs that are
221 followed by IPSPs with a significant delay (Fig. 5h).

222 The thalamic region in both lamprey and mammals is rich in GABAergic cells⁴², which play
223 an important role in thalamic processing in mammals and presumably also here. The thalamic
224 cells are regular spiking with afterhyperpolarisation and postinhibitory rebound (Figs. 5i and
225 5j, Table S1b). Some of the thalamocortical cells, both in a periventricular and lateral
226 location, also send an axonal collateral to the optic tectum (superior colliculus in mammals),
227 and specific thalamic cells target different locations in the tectal retinotopic map (Extended
228 Data Fig. 4). This suggests an overall maintenance of hardwired retinotopic specificity both in
229 thalamus and the visual cortex (Extended Data Fig. 5) in addition to the optic tectum⁴³,
230 similar to what has been described in mammals^{44,45}. The thalamic projection neurons to the
231 visual and somatosensory areas are distinct and separate from those projecting to striatum
232 (Extended Data Fig. 6). Thus, the thalamus has separate subpopulations of neurons relaying
233 visual and somatosensory information to the pallidum, and separately to striatum. While they
234 are clearly distinct, it is uncertain whether they form separate sensory relay nuclei. In
235 conclusion, the lamprey thalamus is a major sensory hub and relays visual and somatosensory
236 information to cortex, as in other vertebrates.

237

238 **Discussion:**

239 From the present study, we can conclude that the lamprey cortex has a visual retinotopic and a
240 somatosensory representation mediated through sensory thalamic projections (Fig. 6a). With
241 respect to specificity, the retinotopy is also present at the level of thalamus with visual
242 thalamocortical neurons receiving retinal input from distinct parts of the optic tract. This
243 implies that the retinotopic organisation is an inherent feature of visual processing at three
244 different levels in the lamprey brain, namely cortex and thalamus in addition to the optic
245 tectum⁴³. The somatosensory information from the dorsal column and the trigeminal afferents
246 are relayed to thalamus through the lemniscal pathways via the dorsal column nucleus and the
247 trigeminal sensory nucleus, respectively. Furthermore, distinct thalamocortical neurons relay
248 visual and somatosensory information to the respective sensory areas in cortex.

249

250 **Cortical microcircuit organisation from an evolutionary perspective**

251 The neocortex has been described as consisting of “canonical circuits”, similar across its
252 sensory and motor areas and across mammals, despite some species-specific differences^{44,46}.
253 In terms of the glutamatergic projection neurons one can identify long-range projection
254 neurons projecting to the brainstem (PT-type), callosal projection neurons targeting the
255 contralateral cortex and striatum (IT-type), and thalamo-recipient neurons of layer 4.
256 Furthermore, it includes the GABAergic interneuron subtypes⁴⁷. A common theme in
257 identifying neocortical homologies has been with a conserved pattern of an input-output

258 connectivity and similar cell types as seen in mammals, reptiles and birds^{16,48-51}. Recently we
259 extended this basic input-output connectivity to the lamprey cortex²⁶, which is further
260 reinforced by our present results. The presence of this basic microcircuit connectivity as well
261 as sensory and motor areas in the cortex of lamprey and mammals presents a compelling case
262 for functional constraints of conservation and evolution of microcircuit features^{26,49}.

263 **Lamination in vertebrate cortices**

264 The neocortex is also distinguished by its lamination - the six-layered cytoarchitecture is
265 ubiquitous in its sensory areas across mammals despite some differences^{22,46}. However, other
266 regions of the mammalian cortex including the piriform cortex and hippocampus are three-
267 layered. The piriform cortex has conserved features with the reptilian three-layered lateral
268 cortex^{52,53}, and the neocortical homologue in non-avian reptiles is considered to be the three-
269 layered dorsal cortex^{26,54}. In lamprey, the visual, somatosensory and the motor areas are
270 present in the dorsal part of the lateral pallium, which is a three-layered laminated cortex²⁶.
271 The corresponding areas in mammals are represented in the occipital, parietal and frontal
272 lobes of neocortex, respectively.

273 **Sensory and motor areas and dorsal pallial homologues**

274 Other than microcircuit features, a striking commonality that can be seen across mammals is
275 neocortical sensory and motor mapping, which seems to adhere to a common regionalisation
276 and modality specific patterning^{7,18}. Despite variations in the neocortical surface area^{22,55}
277 homologous primary sensory areas, including visual and somatosensory areas have been
278 mapped in all mammals examined⁵⁶. Modality specificity of neocortical areas is thus
279 generally agreed upon as a conserved feature present in the last common ancestor of
280 mammals^{7,22,57}. There is evidence, furthermore, to indicate that different sensory modalities
281 are relayed via thalamus in distinct channels to neocortical homologues in both non-avian
282 reptiles and birds^{5,15,19}. The lamprey condition aligns itself closely with mammals in terms of
283 not only representations of distinct visual and somatosensory areas, but also specificity in
284 terms of a retinotopic and a basic somatotopic organisation of these areas in addition to the
285 motor area²⁷. This suggests that the dorsal part of the lateral pallium in lamprey is a dorsal
286 pallial homologue⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰, linking it to the evolutionary ancestry of the mammalian neocortex.
287 The retinotopic specificity is also present at the level of thalamus and as shown earlier in the
288 optic tectum⁴³. It would seem that sensory channels and specificity like retinotopy and
289 somatotopy evolved as a common design of sensorimotor processing very early in vertebrate
290 evolution (see Fig. 6b).

291 **Reconciling marker specificity with function in evolution of cortical cell types**

292 The homology of cell types in the neocortex with its homologue regions in reptiles has been
293 interrogated regarding specificity of marker expression⁶¹. Recent transcriptomic evidence
294 indicates a conservation of “classes” of interneurons, but found differences when comparing
295 for one-to-one homology in marker expression in equivalent glutamatergic cell types between
296 the mammalian neocortex and reptilian dorsal cortex^{54,62}. Nevertheless, the major cell types -
297 the output neurons (layer 5b-equivalent), IT-type and thalamorecipient neurons (layer 4-
298 equivalent) do have similarities in specific marker expression and projection pattern in both
299 non-avian reptiles and birds^{5,50,51,63}, which in essence keeps open the possibility of basic
300 functional cell types and connectivity as an ancestral vertebrate feature. It is conceivable that
301 the diverse cell types found in neocortex are derived from the diversification of the ancestral
302 cell types, which are found also in the lamprey cortex, in addition to the conserved
303 GABAergic interneuron subtypes^{26,50,62,64}. In the lamprey cortex, so far calbindin- and
304 calretinin-expressing GABAergic interneurons have been identified²⁶.

305 **Similarities in the developmental patterning of the telencephalon and pallium**

306 The developing cyclostome embryo shows a remarkable similarity in its telencephalic
307 domains with that of jawed vertebrates, with the major domains present⁶⁵. The vertebrate
308 specific telencephalic homeobox gene *Anf/Hesxl* is also expressed in lamprey⁶⁶. The
309 developing telencephalon in lamprey shows a pallial/subpallial division recognised by *Pax6*
310 gene expression in the pallial region and *DLx1 /2* in the subpallial regions, as well as the
311 immunoreactivity to the *Drosophila* distal-less protein expression in sub-pallium⁶⁷.
312 Furthermore, the expression of *Emx* genes in the pallial domains further adds to the
313 similarities with the jawed vertebrate condition^{65,68,69}. With regard to the GABAergic neurons,
314 one of the sources of the pallial GABAergic neurons, the medial ganglionic eminence (MGE)
315 has also been identified in cyclostomes and the migration of GABAergic neurons from the
316 subpallium (MGE) to pallium has also been shown in lamprey, as in other vertebrates^{65,70,71}.
317 The subdivision of the vertebrate pallium has also been based on the expression of
318 developmental genes, which delineates distinct domains of the developing pallium in
319 vertebrates - the dorsal pallium develops into the neocortex (in mammals and the homologue
320 regions in non-mammals) with the medial pallium forming the hippocampus and the ventral
321 and lateral pallia corresponding to the olfactory regions and the claustrinsular complex^{59,60}.
322 The ancestral vertebrate pallium seems to have at least two pallial subdivisions - dorsal and
323 ventral^{68,72}. In the adult lamprey, the dorsal portion of the lateral pallium has sometimes been
324 suggested, based on the anatomical location, to be the dorsal pallial homologue^{58,73}, which is
325 supported by our present results and our previous functional and connectomic data^{26,27}.

326 **Towards a pan-vertebrate schema for neocortical evolution and a generic forebrain plan**

327 Our data show that a three-layered cortex containing the visual, somatosensory and motor
328 areas (Fig. 6a) characteristic of the mammalian neocortex, as well as the sensory
329 thalamocortical relay is present in the first group of vertebrates that diverged from the
330 vertebrate evolutionary line leading to mammals more than 500 million years ago. In addition,
331 as shown earlier, there is a remarkable level of conservation also at the subcortical level with
332 regard to the basal ganglia, dopamine system and habenula⁷⁴⁻⁷⁸. Taken together, several lines
333 of evidence ranging from developmental, gene expression (i. e. ion channels, receptors,
334 transmitters and peptides expressed in specific neurons), cytoarchitectural, detailed
335 connectomics and function indicate an ancestral origin of the laminated cortex, the basal
336 ganglia and associated structures of mammals. Given this remarkable degree of similarity, it
337 is highly unlikely that these features could have evolved independently through convergence.
338 Consequently, our overarching conclusion is that the basic building-blocks – important parts
339 of the vertebrate forebrain underlying action-selection and decision-making had evolved
340 already at the dawn of vertebrate evolution. These basic features have evidently been retained,
341 whereas other features have been added with evolution and the further development of an
342 extended sensorimotor repertoire and cognition.

343 **Acknowledgments:**

344

345 We would like to thank Profs. Abdel El Manira and Gilad Silberberg and Associate Prof.
346 Peter Wallén for their valuable comments on the manuscript. We are indebted to Dr. Peter
347 Löw for the anti-synaptotagmin antibody. **Funding:** This work was supported by the Swedish
348 Medical Research Council VR-M-K2013-62X-03026, VR-M-2015-02816 and VR-M-2018-
349 02453, the European Union Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant
350 agreement no 604102 (HBP), EU/Horizon 2020 no 720270 (HBP SGA1) and no 785907
351 (HBP SGA2), Parkinsonfonden and the Karolinska Institutet's research funds.

352

353 **Author contributions:**

354

355 SMS and SG conceived the study. SMS, JPF, BR and SG designed the experiments. SMS and
356 JPF did the experiments. All authors participated in data analysis and discussion of results.
357 SG and SMS wrote the manuscript with inputs from BR and JPF. SG supervised all aspects of
358 the study and provided the funding. All correspondence and requests for materials must be
359 addressed to SG (sten.grillner@ki.se).

360

361 **Competing Interests:**

362

363 The authors declare no competing interests.

364

365 **Data Availability:**

366

367 All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article (and its
368 supplementary information files).

369 **Figure legends:**

370 **Fig 1. A visual region in the dorsal part of the lateral pallium responds to retinal**
371 **stimulation with retinotopy.**

372 **a**, Schematic showing the *in vitro* eye-brain preparation used to stimulate the retina while
373 recording in lateral pallium. **b**, Dorsal view of pallium showing the visual area (dashed circle)
374 and the recording sites (colour-coded). **c-f**, For each recording site, only stimulation of a
375 specific location in retina evoked responses (colour-coded), whereas other retinal areas did
376 not (black traces). Bar graphs show significant normalised pallial response amplitude
377 differences. Heatmaps on the right show normalised amplitudes of activity evoked in visual
378 pallium in response to stimulation in multiple retinal locations for each of the recorded areas
379 (n=15). Student's t test; *** indicates $P < 0.001$, and **** indicates $P < 0.0001$. **g**, Heatmap
380 with the combined data from the four recording sites, showing the retinotopy. **h**, The bar
381 graph shows the latency to onset and peak amplitude of the visual response. **i**, Maintaining the
382 eyes intact, activity was evoked in the visual pallium (red asterisks) in response to looming
383 visual stimuli (a dot expanding to cover the entire screen and then shrinking at 1.7 m/s), and
384 black screen presentation (white screen changed to black for three seconds and then back to
385 white). **j-k**, D-glutamate local injections in visual pallium resulted in enhanced responses to
386 retinal stimulation (green trace in **k**), when compared to control (black trace). Local gabazine
387 injection resulted in large responses (red trace in **k**) and a consequent loss of retinotopy
388 (Extended Data Fig. 1). The data are shown as mean \pm s.d. in **h**.

389 **Fig 2. Characterising visual pallial neurons**

390 **a**, Schematic of the brain slice preparation maintaining the thalamus (Th), used for recording
391 from visual pallial neurons, while extracellularly stimulating the optic nerve at the entrance to
392 the chiasm. **b**, Spiking (black) and EPSPs (blue) elicited in two visual pallial cells held at rest
393 in response to repetitive stimulation of the optic nerve. **c**, When the cell was held at more
394 depolarised membrane potentials with continuous spiking, nerve stimulation resulted in a
395 cessation of spiking. **d**, Optic nerve stimulation eliciting subthreshold EPSPs in control
396 conditions (blue trace), resulted in spiking after gabazine (bath-applied, red traces). **e**, EPSP
397 amplitudes elicited in visual pallial neurons in response to repetitive nerve stimulation
398 (normalised to the first EPSP). **f-g**, Morphology of a visual pallial cell with one of its
399 dendrites extending into the medial pallium in the region where thalamic fibers enter. **h**,
400 Locations of the recorded visual pallial cells. **i**, Current-voltage plot of steady-state

401 subthreshold voltage deflections of a visual pallial cell. **j**, Firing properties of visual pallial
402 neurons: spike elicited in response to a brief (5 ms) suprathreshold current pulse showing the
403 afterhyperpolarisation at holding potential of -50 mV and at rest. **k**, Responses to 1 s
404 hyperpolarising and depolarising current pulses (step 10 pA), showing threshold response
405 (blue trace), suprathreshold response (red trace) and postinhibitory rebound spiking (green
406 trace). See Extended Data Fig. 2 and Supplementary Table S1. Abbreviations: dmtn,
407 dorsomedial telencephalic nucleus; LPal, lateral pallium; MPal, medial pallium; OB, olfactory
408 bulb; OT, optic tectum; ot, optic tract; SC, spinal cord.

409

410 **Fig 3. Somatosensory region in the dorsal part of the lateral pallium**

411 **a**, Schematic showing the *in vitro* preparation and the recording and stimulation points used.
412 **b**, Responses recorded in the dorsal part of the lateral pallium following extracellular
413 repetitive stimulation (4 pulses) of the trigeminal sensory nerve (blue trace) and the dorsal
414 column (pink trace). **c**, Areas responding to trigeminal and dorsal column stimulation are
415 located adjacent to each other (blue and pink dots, respectively) forming the somatosensory
416 area (blue), distinct from the visual (mauve) and motor (green) areas. **d**, The bar graph shows
417 delay for onset of response and delay to peak amplitude following trigeminal nerve
418 stimulation. **e**, The bar graph shows delay for onset of response and delay to peak amplitude
419 following dorsal column stimulation. **f**, Retrogradely labelled cells in the dorsal column
420 nucleus (DCN; dotted white circle) from Neurobiotin injections in the contralateral thalamus
421 (inset left). **g-h**, Anterogradely labelled dorsal column axons (blue in **g** and **h**) following
422 dextran injections in the dorsal column (inset in **g**), forming synapses (green in **h**) on a
423 dendrite of a retrogradely labelled DCN neuron targeting the contralateral thalamus (injection
424 site inset in **g**; magenta in **g** and **h**). Synapses immunolabelled with synaptotagmin (white
425 arrowheads in **h**). **i**, Anterogradely labelled axons in the contralateral thalamus (white
426 arrowheads) following Neurobiotin injections in the DCN (inset). **j-l**, A thalamopallial cell,
427 retrogradely labelled from somatosensory pallium (**j**, yellow) for whole-cell recording and
428 intracellular Neurobiotin injection (**k** and **l**, magenta). The anterogradely labelled axons from
429 the contralateral DCN (**l**, blue) form synapses (**l**, green) on dendrite of the thalamopallial
430 neuron. Synapses are immunostained for synaptotagmin. **m-o**, Schematics of the lamprey
431 brain showing the experimental design and somatosensory pathways in **f-l**. The data are
432 shown as mean \pm s.d. in **d** and **e**. See also Extended Data Figs. 3 and 6.

433

434 **Fig 4. Projections from the dorsal column nucleus to thalamus.**

435 **a**, Transverse schematic sections of the lamprey brain from the level of thalamus to the obex,
436 showing the injection site of Neurobiotin in the dorsal column nucleus (DCN, red) and
437 anterogradely labelled DCN fibres (related sections to subsequent photomicrographs indicated
438 in black squares). The DCN fibres are largely contralateral and they cross at the level of DCN
439 and ascend as the lemniscal bundle to terminate in thalamus. **b-g**, Photomicrographs of
440 transverse sections of the lamprey brain showing the DCN-thalamic tract (magenta, encircled
441 in dotted white lines) at the level of (**b**) pretectum, (**c**), rostral optic tectum, (**d**) caudal optic
442 tectum, (**e**) nucleus V, (**f**) caudal MRRN, (**g**) caudal PRRN, white arrows showing the
443 crossing of the fiber tract. Abbreviations: ARRN, anterior rhombencephalic reticular nucleus;
444 dV, descending trigeminal afferents; EmTh, eminentia thalami; fr, fasciculus retroflexus; GP,
445 globus pallidus; Hb, habenula; Hyp, hypothalamus; MAM, Mammillary area, MRRN, middle
446 rhombencephalic reticular nucleus; M3, Müller cell 3; M5, mesencephalic M5 nucleus of
447 Schober; nVs, trigeminal nerve sensory root; nIII, oculomotor nerve; nVm, trigeminal nerve
448 motor root; PRRN, posterior rhombencephalic reticular nucleus; STN, subthalamic nucleus;
449 V, trigeminal motor nucleus; VII, facial; X, vagal motor nucleus.

450

451 **Fig 5. Thalamic relay to the visual area**

452 **a**, Schematic showing tracer injection to retrogradely label thalamopallial neurons. **b**,
453 Morphology of the thalamopallial cell (d-f). The dendrites extend into the optic tract. **c**, An
454 optic tract axon (magenta) synapses onto a dendrite (blue, dotted square in b) indicated by
455 synaptotagmin (green). **d**, Repetitive stimulation in one position of the optic tract elicits
456 EPSPs/spiking (ON Pos1) in a thalamopallial neuron, while another position provides very
457 small EPSPs (OFF Pos 2). **e**, Holding the cell at more depolarised membrane potential elicits
458 spiking, which is silenced by stimulation of both optic tract positions. **f**, Gabazine bath
459 application in thalamus results in a large response and loss of specificity. **g-h**, EPSPs (blue
460 traces) and IPSPs (red traces) recorded at different holding potentials in a thalamic cell
461 (QX314 in the recording pipette to block spiking) following stimulation of the optic tract. The
462 EPSPs are facilitatory (graph in g) and precede the IPSPs significantly in their latency
463 (histograms in h, n=9). **i**, Firing properties of thalamopallial neurons: spikes elicited in
464 response to brief (5 ms) suprathreshold current pulse showing the afterhyperpolarisation.
465 Membrane potential responses to 1 s hyperpolarising and depolarising current pulses (step 10
466 pA) showing threshold (blue trace) and suprathreshold response (red trace). A long
467 suprathreshold (10s) pulse elicits non-adapting regular-spiking behaviour and a
468 hyperpolarising pulse elicits postinhibitory rebound spiking. The data are shown as mean
469 \pm s.d. in **h**. Students t test; ** indicates $P < 0.01$. See also Extended Data Figs. 4-6 and
470 Supplementary Table S1. Abbreviations: Hb, habenula; Hyp, hypothalamus; OB, olfactory
471 bulb; OT, optic tectum.

472
473 **Fig 6. Visual, somatosensory and motor organisation in the lamprey cortex and in the**
474 **phylogenetic vertebrate tree** **a**, Summarising schematic of lamprey cortex showing
475 retinotopic visual areas, somatosensory areas and motor areas as well as the retinal, trigeminal
476 and dorsal column nucleus afferents relayed via distinct subpopulations of thalamic neurons.
477 **b**, Phylogenetic tree of vertebrates indicating the current knowledge regarding the presence of
478 layered cortices and distinct sensory and motor areas.

480
481 **Materials and Methods**

482 **Animals**

483 Experiments were performed on 88 adult river lampreys (*Lampetra fluviatilis*) and 8 newly
484 transformed sea lampreys (*Petromyzon marinus*). The experimental procedures were
485 approved by the local ethics committee (*Stockholms Norra Djurförsöksetiska Nämnd*) and
486 were in accordance with The Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (1996).
487 Every effort was made to minimize suffering and to reduce the number of animals used
488 during the study.

489
490 **Extracellular recordings**

491 To record extracellular activity in lateral pallium/cortex in response to visual (n=9) or
492 somatosensory (n=16) stimulation, we used an *in situ* preparation exposing the brain and
493 rostral segments of the spinal cord maintaining the eyes. Animals were deeply anaesthetised
494 with MS-222 (100 mgL⁻¹; Sigma Aldrich) and decapitated. The dorsal skin, cartilage and
495 muscles were removed to expose the brain, and the lens was removed to expose the retina.
496 The preparation was then pinned down in a cooling chamber perfused continuously with

497 artificial cerebrospinal fluid (aCSF, 6–8°C), with the following composition (in mM): 125
498 NaCl, 2.6 KCl, 1 MgCl₂, 2 CaCl₂, 25 NaHCO₃, 10 glucose. Local field potentials (LFPs) were
499 recorded using tungsten microelectrodes (~1-5 MΩ), connected to a 4-channel MA102
500 amplifier (Elektroniklabor, Zoologie, University of Cologne), and digitised at 20 kHz using
501 PClamp 10 (Molecular Devices) software. For electrical stimulation of the retina, dorsal
502 column or trigeminal nerve, borosilicate glass microcapillaries connected to a stimulus
503 isolation unit (MI401; Elektroniklabor, Zoologie) were used. The stimulation intensity was
504 generally set to minimal strength necessary for evoking LFPs, and controls made to check for
505 potential current spread. For visual stimulation via a screen (n=8), the same preparation was
506 used albeit with the eyes intact, pinned down in a transparent chamber facing the centre of a
507 computer screen placed in a lateral position at ~30 cm distance. Visual stimuli were generated
508 using custom code in Matlab, using the Psychophysics Toolbox extension and coordinated
509 with the electrophysiological acquisition software PClamp using a Master-8 programmable
510 pulse generator (AMPI Instruments). Experiments were carried out in darkness, and prior to
511 each experiment the preparation was left to adapt to a white screen (used as the background
512 for the applied stimuli), for at least 30 mins.

513 During the extracellular recordings, the GABA_A-receptor antagonist gabazine (10 μM;
514 Tocris; n=8) or D-glutamate (10 μM; Sigma-Aldrich; n=2) were locally applied in visual
515 pallium by pressure injection, using a borosilicate glass micropipette (Hilgenberg GmbH,
516 Malsfeld) fixed to a holder attached to a Picospritzer-II Microinjection Dispense System
517 (Parker). The holder was connected to a MP-285 motorized micromanipulator (Sutter
518 Instruments), so that the position of the pipette could be monitored to ensure drug injections
519 in the region of interest. Fast Green dye was used to aid visualisation of the injection.

520

521 **Retrograde labelling and whole-cell recordings**

522 To retrogradely label thalamic neurons projecting to the visual cortex/pallium prior to the
523 patch clamp recordings (n=11), 50-100 nL rhodamine conjugated dextran amine (10 kDa;
524 12% in aCSF; Molecular Probes) was injected unilaterally into the visual area of the lateral
525 pallium. Following injections, the dorsal skin was sutured, and the animals returned to their
526 aquarium for 48-72 hs to allow for transport of the tracer. The animals were then deeply
527 anaesthetised and decapitated, and the brains removed and embedded in agar (4% dissolved in
528 aCSF; Sigma-Aldrich). Transverse slices of thalamus (300-350 μm) were cut on a vibrating
529 microtome. The slice was continuously perfused with aCSF at 6-8°C. Neurons were visualised
530 with DIC/infrared optics (Olympus BX51WI, Tokyo, Japan). Retrogradely labelled
531 fluorescent cells were visualised using a mercury lamp (Olympus U-RFL-T).

532 For the preparation utilised to record from neurons in the visual area in lateral pallium
533 while extracellularly stimulating the optic nerve at the entrance to the chiasm (n=9), the angle
534 of sectioning was adjusted in such a way that both the visual area in lateral pallium and the
535 optic nerve/chiasm were included and could be visualised. A thick slice (~2 mm) maintaining
536 thalamus was mounted in a recording chamber continuously perfused with aCSF at 6-8°C and
537 allowed to recover for one hour. Whole-cell patch clamp recordings were performed with
538 microcapillaries made from borosilicate glass using a vertical puller (Model PP-830;
539 Narishige). The resistance of recording pipettes was 7–12 MΩ when filled with an
540 intracellular solution of the following composition (in mM): 130 potassium gluconate, 5 KCl,

541 10 phosphocreatine disodium salt, 10 HEPES, 4 Mg-ATP, 0.3 Na-GTP; (osmolarity 265–275
542 mOsmol). In some cases, the electrode solution also included 2 mM of triethylammonium
543 bromide (QX314; Sigma-Aldrich) to block action potentials. Bridge balance and pipette-
544 capacitance compensation were adjusted using a MultiClamp 700B patch clamp amplifier and
545 Digidata 1322 analog-to-digital converter under software control PClamp 10. Membrane
546 potential values were not corrected for the liquid junction potential.

547 Electrical stimulation of the optic tract (n=9) was performed with borosilicate glass
548 microcapillaries connected to a stimulus isolation unit. The stimulation intensity was set to 1-
549 2 times the threshold strength (10–100 μ A) to evoke post synaptic potentials. To investigate
550 the short-term dynamics of synaptic transmission, a stimulus train of 8 pulses at 10 Hz was
551 used followed by a recovery pulse 1-2 s after the 8th pulse to assess the return of the
552 membrane to rest.

553

554 **Morphological reconstructions**

555 Neurons were intracellularly injected with 0.3–0.5% Neurobiotin (Vector Laboratories),
556 during patch clamp recordings. Brain slices were fixed overnight in 4% formaldehyde and
557 14% picric acid in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (PB). Following a thorough rinse in phosphate
558 buffered saline (PBS), the slices were incubated in streptavidin conjugated to Cy2, Cy3 or
559 Cy5 (1:1000, Jackson ImmunoResearch) in 0.3% Triton X-100 and 1% BSA in 0.1 M PB for
560 two hours at room temperature. The slices were then rinsed in 0.01 M PBS and mounted in
561 glycerol containing 2.5% DABCO (Sigma-Aldrich).

562

563 **Anatomical tract tracing**

564 Lampreys were deeply anesthetised with MS-222 (100 mg/L), and transected at the level of
565 the seventh gill. The dorsal skin and cartilage were removed to expose the brain. The head
566 was pinned down and submerged in ice cooled oxygenated HEPES buffered physiological
567 solution (in mM; 138 NaCl, 2.1 KCl, 1.8 CaCl₂, 1.2 MgCl₂, 4 glucose, and 2 HEPES), pH 7.4.
568 All injections were made with glass micropipettes. Micropipettes were fixed to a
569 micromanipulator, and 50 nL Neurobiotin (20% wt/vol) in aCSF containing Fast Green (to aid
570 visualisation of the tracer) was pressure injected in the DCN (n=5) or thalamus (n=4). In
571 addition, dual injections were also performed with Neurobiotin in the thalamus to retrogradely
572 label neurons in the trigeminal sensory nucleus along with rhodamine-dextran amine injected
573 into the trigeminal nerve to anterogradely label trigeminal afferents (n=3). The brains were
574 left in HEPES solution overnight to allow transport of the tracer. Brains were dissected out
575 and fixed in 4% formaldehyde and 14% saturated picric acid in 0.1 M PB, pH 7.4, for 12–24
576 h, and then cryoprotected in 20% sucrose in 0.1 M PB for 3–12 h. 30 μ m thick transverse
577 sections were cut using a cryostat, collected on gelatin-coated slides, and stored at –20°C
578 until further processing. For detection of Neurobiotin, streptavidin conjugated to AMCA,
579 Cy2, Cy3 or Cy5 (1:1000; Jackson ImmunoResearch) was mixed with a deep red, green or
580 AMCA Nissl stain (1:1000; Molecular Probes) diluted in 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA),
581 0.3% Triton X-100 in 0.1 M PB and applied for 2 hs. Following several rinses in 0.01 M PBS,
582 the sections were mounted as described above.

583 In order to retrogradely label subgroups of thalamotectal projection neurons, 50-100
584 nL rhodamine-dextran amine (10 kDa; 12% in aCSF) was injected into the caudal tectum and

585 50-100 nL Alexa Fluor 647-dextran amine (10 kDa; 12% in aCSF) was injected into the
586 rostral tectum (n=5). In some cases, this was combined with injections of Neurobiotin (20%
587 in aCSF) in the pallium (n=3). Triple tracer injections were performed to label distinct
588 thalamic neurons targeting different sensory areas in pallium and striatum. Rhodamine-
589 dextran amine was injected into visual pallium and Alexa Fluor 647-dextran amine was
590 injected into somatosensory pallium, along with injections of 50 nL of Neurobiotin in striatum
591 (n=4). Dual injections were performed using Neurobiotin in the thalamus to retrogradely label
592 neurons in DCN and Alexa Fluor 647-dextran amine in the dorsal column (n=4) to
593 anterogradely label dorsal column axons in DCN. Following injections, the animals were
594 returned to their aquarium for one or two days to allow the tracers to be transported. Animals
595 were subsequently sacrificed and brains were fixed and processed as described above.

596

597 **Tracing and morphology combined with synaptotagmin immunohistochemistry**

598 For combining retrograde labelling of neurons for whole-cell recordings and tracing,
599 rhodamine-dextran amine was injected into visual/somatosensory pallium to label thalamic
600 neurons and Alexa 647-dextran amine was injected into either tectum to retrogradely label the
601 optic tract (n=3) or into the DCN to anterogradely label fibres targeting thalamus (n=3).
602 Following tracer injections, the animals were returned to their aquarium and sacrificed after
603 one or two days. Whole-cell recordings were performed on identified thalamic neurons, which
604 were intracellularly injected with Neurobiotin for morphological analysis. The slices were
605 fixed overnight, and subsequently incubated overnight with a rabbit anti-synaptotagmin
606 antibody (1:2000; kind gift from Dr. Peter Löw, for Western blot analysis²⁶). Following a
607 thorough rinse in PBS the sections were incubated for 12 hs with a mixture of Cy2 or Cy3
608 conjugated donkey anti-mouse IgG (1:500; Jackson ImmunoResearch), and AMCA, Cy2,
609 Cy3 or Cy5 conjugated streptavidin (1:1000; Jackson ImmunoResearch) and when required,
610 slices were also counterstained with an AMCA, Alexa 488 or deep red fluorescent Nissl stain.
611 All primary and secondary antibodies as well as streptavidin were diluted in 0.3% Triton X-
612 100 and 1% BSA in 0.1 M PB. Slices were mounted as above.

613

614 **Image Analysis**

615 Photomicrographs were taken with a digital camera mounted on an Olympus BX51
616 fluorescence microscope. Illustrations were prepared in Adobe Illustrator and Adobe
617 Photoshop CC. Images were only adjusted for brightness and contrast. Confocal Z-stacks of
618 optical sections were obtained using a Zeiss Laser scanning microscope (LSM 510 or 880),
619 and the projection images were processed using the Zeiss ZEN software and Adobe
620 Photoshop CC.

621

622 **Data analysis**

623 Analysis of extracellular data was done using custom written functions in Matlab. To generate
624 the bar-graphs showing comparisons of 'ON' vs 'OFF' amplitudes, maximum amplitudes of
625 fully rectified LFPs were calculated using the numerical integrator function 'trapz' (Matlab),
626 which employs the trapezoidal method to approximate the integral over a defined interval.
627 The baseline amplitude for a particular experiment (when there was no stimulus evoked
628 activity) was subtracted from both 'ON' and 'OFF' amplitudes. The resulting amplitudes

629 were normalised for the maximal ‘OFF’ amplitude. The average values for the normalised
630 ‘ON’ and ‘OFF’ amplitudes as well as the SD were then calculated and plotted.

631 For generating the heatmaps of retinal responses, stimulation sites in the retina were
632 mapped onto a surface illustration of the retina. Amplitudes of the LFPs generated for each
633 stimulation point were calculated as described above for a particular recording site in the
634 visual pallium. Heatmaps for each recording site and their corresponding normalised response
635 amplitudes were generated in Matlab using built in functions. The range for the colour scale
636 was set between 6.5 to 10.

637 For intracellular data analysis, only neurons with resting membrane potentials more
638 hyperpolarised than -50 mV upon entering whole-cell recording configuration, and with over-
639 shooting action potentials were included in the dataset for subsequent analysis. All recordings
640 were performed in whole-cell configuration and current clamp mode, with injections of
641 hyperpolarising and depolarising current steps to investigate voltage responses. Depolarising
642 current injections were also given in a ramp-like manner to measure rheobase and threshold.
643 Data analysis was performed using custom-written functions in Matlab or using PClamp 10.
644 Several parameters were obtained from recorded cells. Resting membrane potential was
645 measured without DC current injection a few minutes after entering whole-cell recording
646 configuration. Input resistance was calculated as the slope of the regression line fit to steady-
647 state membrane potential responses to a hyperpolarising 5 pA current injection from rest. The
648 current injections were limited to this value to minimize the triggering of voltage-gated
649 conductances, which would influence the input resistance. Membrane time constant was the
650 time taken for the membrane potential to reach 63% of the maximal hyperpolarised value for
651 a 5 pA, 500 ms negative current injection from rest. Voltage threshold for evoking action
652 potentials was the value of the membrane potential at which its first derivative (dV/dt) crossed
653 10 mV in response to gradual depolarisation from resting potential in a ramp-like manner.
654 Rheobase was the minimal current to attain threshold and elicit an action potential in response
655 to depolarising current injection in a ramp-like manner from rest. Spike amplitude was the
656 height of the spike measured from threshold, and spike half-width was the width measured at
657 half the spike amplitude. In order to separately record synaptic excitatory and inhibitory
658 responses, the membrane potential was held close to the reversal potential for IPSPs and
659 EPSPs, -65 mV and -20 mV, respectively. It was difficult to hold the cell at more depolarised
660 membrane potentials than -20 mV without losing stable recording conditions.

661

662 **Statistical analysis**

663 For statistical analysis, we performed two-sample unpaired or paired Student’s t tests using
664 Matlab. Throughout the figures, sample statistics are expressed as means \pm SD (Standard
665 deviation) or means \pm SEM (Standard error of mean). In the figures, significance levels are
666 indicated as follows: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$.

667
668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676
677
678
679
680
681
682
683
684
685
686
687
688
689
690
691
692
693
694
695
696
697
698
699
700
701
702
703
704
705
706
707
708
709
710
711
712
713
714
715
716
717
718
719
720
721
722
723
724

References:

- 1 Kumar, S. & Hedges, S. B. A molecular timescale for vertebrate evolution. *Nature* **392**, 917-920, doi:10.1038/31927 (1998).
- 2 Suzuki, D. G. & Grillner, S. The stepwise development of the lamprey visual system and its evolutionary implications. *Biol Rev Camb Philos Soc* **93**, 1461-1477, doi:10.1111/brv.12403 (2018).
- 3 Suzuki, D. G., Perez-Fernandez, J., Wibble, T., Kardamakis, A. A. & Grillner, S. The role of the optic tectum for visually evoked orienting and evasive movements. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **116**, 15272-15281, doi:10.1073/pnas.1907962116 (2019).
- 4 Woolsey, C. N. Organization of somatic sensory and motor areas of the cerebral cortex. *Biological and Biochemical Bases of Behaviour*, 63-81 (1958).
- 5 Dugas-Ford, J. & Ragsdale, C. W. Levels of homology and the problem of neocortex. *Annu Rev Neurosci* **38**, 351-368, doi:10.1146/annurev-neuro-071714-033911 (2015).
- 6 Briscoe, S. D. & Ragsdale, C. W. Evolution of the Chordate Telencephalon. *Curr Biol* **29**, R647-R662, doi:10.1016/j.cub.2019.05.026 (2019).
- 7 Kaas, J. H. The evolution of brains from early mammals to humans. *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Cogn Sci* **4**, 33-45, doi:10.1002/wcs.1206 (2013).
- 8 Harting, J. K., Huerta, M. F., Hashikawa, T. & van Lieshout, D. P. Projection of the mammalian superior colliculus upon the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus: organization of tectogeniculate pathways in nineteen species. *J Comp Neurol* **304**, 275-306, doi:10.1002/cne.903040210 (1991).
- 9 Tohmi, M., Meguro, R., Tsukano, H., Hishida, R. & Shibuki, K. The extrageniculate visual pathway generates distinct response properties in the higher visual areas of mice. *Curr Biol* **24**, 587-597, doi:10.1016/j.cub.2014.01.061 (2014).
- 10 Berkley, K. J. Spatial relationships between the terminations of somatic sensory and motor pathways in the rostral brainstem of cats and monkeys. I. Ascending somatic sensory inputs to lateral diencephalon. *J Comp Neurol* **193**, 283-317, doi:10.1002/cne.901930119 (1980).
- 11 Casas-Torremocha, D., Clasca, F. & Nunez, A. Posterior Thalamic Nucleus Modulation of Tactile Stimuli Processing in Rat Motor and Primary Somatosensory Cortices. *Front Neural Circuits* **11**, 69, doi:10.3389/fncir.2017.00069 (2017).
- 12 Guido, W. Development, form, and function of the mouse visual thalamus. *J Neurophysiol* **120**, 211-225, doi:10.1152/jn.00651.2017 (2018).
- 13 Fournier, J., Muller, C. M., Schneider, I. & Laurent, G. Spatial Information in a Non-retinotopic Visual Cortex. *Neuron* **97**, 164-180 e167, doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2017.11.017 (2018).
- 14 Laurent, G. *et al.* in *Micro-, Meso- and Macro-Dynamics of the Brain* (eds G. Buzsaki & Y. Christen) 23-33 (2016).
- 15 Butler, A. B. The evolution of the dorsal pallium in the telencephalon of amniotes: cladistic analysis and a new hypothesis. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev* **19**, 66-101 (1994).
- 16 Karten, H. J. The organization of the avian telencephalon and some speculations on the phylogeny of the amniote telencephalon*. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* **167**, 164-179, doi:10.1111/j.1749-6632.1969.tb20442.x (1969).
- 17 Karten, H. J. Neocortical evolution: neuronal circuits arise independently of lamination. *Curr Biol* **23**, R12-15, doi:10.1016/j.cub.2012.11.013 (2013).
- 18 Krubitzer, L. The magnificent compromise: cortical field evolution in mammals. *Neuron* **56**, 201-208, doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2007.10.002 (2007).
- 19 Medina, L. & Reiner, A. Do birds possess homologues of mammalian primary visual, somatosensory and motor cortices? *Trends Neurosci* **23**, 1-12 (2000).
- 20 Wild, J. M. The avian somatosensory system: the pathway from wing to Wulst in a passerine (Chloris chloris). *Brain Res* **759**, 122-134, doi:10.1016/s0006-8993(97)00253-9 (1997).
- 21 Wild, J. M. in *Sturkie's Avian Physiology* (ed C. G. Scanes) Ch. 5, 55-69 (Academic Press, 2015).
- 22 Defelipe, J. The evolution of the brain, the human nature of cortical circuits, and intellectual creativity. *Front Neuroanat* **5**, 29, doi:10.3389/fnana.2011.00029 (2011).
- 23 Karamian, A. I., Vesselkin, N. P., Belekova, M. G. & Zagorulko, T. M. Electrophysiological characteristics of tectal and thalamo-cortical divisions of the visual system in lower vertebrates. *J Comp Neurol* **127**, 559-576, doi:10.1002/cne.901270408 (1966).
- 24 Northcutt, R. G. & Wicht, H. Afferent and efferent connections of the lateral and medial pallia of the silver lamprey. *Brain Behav Evol* **49**, 1-19, doi:10.1159/000112978 (1997).
- 25 Wicht, H. & Northcutt, R. G. Telencephalic connections in the Pacific hagfish (*Eptatretus stouti*), with special reference to the thalamopallial system. *J Comp Neurol* **395**, 245-260 (1998).

- 725 26 Suryanarayana, S. M., Robertson, B., Wallen, P. & Grillner, S. The Lamprey Pallium Provides a
726 Blueprint of the Mammalian Layered Cortex. *Curr Biol* **27**, 3264-3277 e3265,
727 doi:10.1016/j.cub.2017.09.034 (2017).
- 728 27 Ocana, F. M. *et al.* The lamprey pallium provides a blueprint of the mammalian motor projections from
729 cortex. *Curr Biol* **25**, 413-423, doi:10.1016/j.cub.2014.12.013 (2015).
- 730 28 Northcutt, R. G. & Ronan, M. Afferent and efferent connections of the bullfrog medial pallium. *Brain*
731 *Behav Evol* **40**, 1-16, doi:10.1159/000113898 (1992).
- 732 29 Cohen, D. H., Duff, T. A. & Ebbesson, S. O. Electrophysiological identification of a visual area in
733 shark telencephalon. *Science* **182**, 492-494 (1973).
- 734 30 Ishikawa, Y. *et al.* Developmental origin of diencephalic sensory relay nuclei in teleosts. *Brain Behav*
735 *Evol* **69**, 87-95, doi:10.1159/000095197 (2007).
- 736 31 Ito, H., Murakami, T., Fukuoka, T. & Kishida, R. Thalamic fiber connections in a teleost (*Sebastiscus*
737 *marmoratus*): visual somatosensory, octavolateral, and cerebellar relay region to the telencephalon. *J*
738 *Comp Neurol* **250**, 215-227, doi:10.1002/cne.902500208 (1986).
- 739 32 Vernier, P. in *The Evolution of Nervous Systems in Non-Mammalian Vertebrates*. (ed J. H. Kaas)
740 (Academic Press, 2017).
- 741 33 Yamamoto, N. *et al.* A new interpretation on the homology of the teleostean telencephalon based on
742 hodology and a new eversion model. *Brain Behav Evol* **69**, 96-104, doi:10.1159/000095198 (2007).
- 743 34 Yamamoto, N. & Ito, H. Fiber connections of the anterior preglomerular nucleus in cyprinids with notes
744 on telencephalic connections of the preglomerular complex. *J Comp Neurol* **491**, 212-233,
745 doi:10.1002/cne.20681 (2005).
- 746 35 Kardamakis, A. A., Saitoh, K. & Grillner, S. Tectal microcircuit generating visual selection commands
747 on gaze-controlling neurons. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **112**, E1956-1965,
748 doi:10.1073/pnas.1504866112 (2015).
- 749 36 Perez-Fernandez, J., Kardamakis, A. A., Suzuki, D. G., Robertson, B. & Grillner, S. Direct
750 Dopaminergic Projections from the SNc Modulate Visuomotor Transformation in the Lamprey Tectum.
751 *Neuron* **96**, 910-924 e915, doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2017.09.051 (2017).
- 752 37 Dubuc, R., Bongianini, F., Ohta, Y. & Grillner, S. Anatomical and physiological study of brainstem
753 nuclei relaying dorsal column inputs in lampreys. *J Comp Neurol* **327**, 260-270,
754 doi:10.1002/cne.903270208 (1993).
- 755 38 Nieuwenhuys, R., Nicholson, C. in *The central nervous system of vertebrates* Vol. 1 (ed H.J.
756 Donkelaar, and Nicholson, C.) (Springer, 1997).
- 757 39 de Miguel, E., Rodicio, M. C. & Anadon, R. Organization of the visual system in larval lampreys: an
758 HRP study. *J Comp Neurol* **302**, 529-542, doi:10.1002/cne.903020309 (1990).
- 759 40 Heier, P. Fundamental principles in the structure of the brain. A study of the brain of *Petromyzon*
760 *fluviatilis*. *Acta Anatomica Supplement* **6**, 1-213 (1948).
- 761 41 Kennedy, M. C. & Rubinson, K. Retinal projections in larval, transforming and adult sea lamprey,
762 *Petromyzon marinus*. *J Comp Neurol* **171**, 465-479, doi:10.1002/cne.901710404 (1977).
- 763 42 Robertson, B., Auclair, F., Menard, A., Grillner, S. & Dubuc, R. GABA distribution in lamprey is
764 phylogenetically conserved. *J Comp Neurol* **503**, 47-63, doi:10.1002/cne.21348 (2007).
- 765 43 Jones, M. R., Grillner, S. & Robertson, B. Selective projection patterns from subtypes of retinal
766 ganglion cells to tectum and pretectum: distribution and relation to behavior. *J Comp Neurol* **517**, 257-
767 275, doi:10.1002/cne.22203 (2009).
- 768 44 Douglas, R. J. & Martin, K. A. Neuronal circuits of the neocortex. *Annu Rev Neurosci* **27**, 419-451,
769 doi:10.1146/annurev.neuro.27.070203.144152 (2004).
- 770 45 Ferster, D., Chung, S. & Wheat, H. Orientation selectivity of thalamic input to simple cells of cat visual
771 cortex. *Nature* **380**, 249-252, doi:10.1038/380249a0 (1996).
- 772 46 Goulas, A., Majka, P., Rosa, M. G. P. & Hilgetag, C. C. A blueprint of mammalian cortical
773 connectomes. *PLoS Biol* **17**, e2005346, doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.2005346 (2019).
- 774 47 Markram, H. *et al.* Interneurons of the neocortical inhibitory system. *Nat Rev Neurosci* **5**, 793-807,
775 doi:10.1038/nrn1519 (2004).
- 776 48 Harris, K. D. & Shepherd, G. M. The neocortical circuit: themes and variations. *Nat Neurosci* **18**, 170-
777 181, doi:10.1038/nn.3917 (2015).
- 778 49 Shepherd, G. M. The microcircuit concept applied to cortical evolution: from three-layer to six-layer
779 cortex. *Front Neuroanat* **5**, 30, doi:10.3389/fnana.2011.00030 (2011).
- 780 50 Briscoe, S. D. & Ragsdale, C. W. Homology, neocortex, and the evolution of developmental
781 mechanisms. *Science* **362**, 190-193, doi:10.1126/science.aau3711 (2018).
- 782 51 Karten, H. J. Vertebrate brains and evolutionary connectomics: on the origins of the mammalian
783 'neocortex'. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci* **370**, doi:10.1098/rstb.2015.0060 (2015).

784 52 Klingler, E. Development and Organization of the Evolutionarily Conserved Three-Layered Olfactory
785 Cortex. *eNeuro* **4**, doi:10.1523/ENEURO.0193-16.2016 (2017).

786 53 Fournier, J., Muller, C. M. & Laurent, G. Looking for the roots of cortical sensory computation in
787 three-layered cortices. *Curr Opin Neurobiol* **31**, 119-126, doi:10.1016/j.conb.2014.09.006 (2015).

788 54 Tosches, M. A. *et al.* Evolution of pallium, hippocampus, and cortical cell types revealed by single-cell
789 transcriptomics in reptiles. *Science* **360**, 881-888, doi:10.1126/science.aar4237 (2018).

790 55 Raghanti, M. A., Munger, E.A., Wicinski, B., Butti, C., Jacobs, B., Hof, P.R. in *In Evolution of Nervous*
791 *Systems 2e* Vol. Volume 4 (ed J.H. Kaas) 267-289 (Elsevier., 2017).

792 56 Brodmann, K. *Brodmann's: Localisation in the Cerebral Cortex.* (Springer US, 2006).

793 57 Krubitzer, L. A. & Prescott, T. J. The Combinatorial Creature: Cortical Phenotypes within and across
794 Lifetimes. *Trends Neurosci* **41**, 744-762, doi:10.1016/j.tins.2018.08.002 (2018).

795 58 Pombal, M. A., Megias, M., Bardet, S. M. & Puelles, L. New and old thoughts on the segmental
796 organization of the forebrain in lampreys. *Brain Behav Evol* **74**, 7-19, doi:10.1159/000229009 (2009).

797 59 Puelles, L. Comments on the Updated Tetrartite Pallium Model in the Mouse and Chick, Featuring a
798 Homologous Claustrum-Insular Complex. *Brain Behav Evol* **90**, 171-189, doi:10.1159/000479782
799 (2017).

800 60 Puelles, L., Alonso, A., Garcia-Calero, E. & Martinez-de-la-Torre, M. Concentric ring topology of
801 mammalian cortical sectors and relevance for patterning studies. *J Comp Neurol* **527**, 1731-1752,
802 doi:10.1002/cne.24650 (2019).

803 61 Montiel, J. F. & Aboitiz, F. Homology in Amniote Brain Evolution: The Rise of Molecular Evidence.
804 *Brain Behav Evol* **91**, 59-64, doi:10.1159/000489116 (2018).

805 62 Tosches, M. A. & Laurent, G. Evolution of neuronal identity in the cerebral cortex. *Curr Opin*
806 *Neurobiol* **56**, 199-208, doi:10.1016/j.conb.2019.04.009 (2019).

807 63 Dugas-Ford, J., Rowell, J. J. & Ragsdale, C. W. Cell-type homologies and the origins of the neocortex.
808 *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **109**, 16974-16979, doi:10.1073/pnas.1204773109 (2012).

809 64 Huang, Z. J. & Paul, A. The diversity of GABAergic neurons and neural communication elements. *Nat*
810 *Rev Neurosci* **20**, 563-572, doi:10.1038/s41583-019-0195-4 (2019).

811 65 Sugahara, F. *et al.* Evidence from cyclostomes for complex regionalization of the ancestral vertebrate
812 brain. *Nature* **531**, 97-100, doi:10.1038/nature16518 (2016).

813 66 Bayramov, A. V. *et al.* The presence of *Anf/Hesx1* homeobox gene in lampreys suggests that it could
814 play an important role in emergence of telencephalon. *Sci Rep* **6**, 39849, doi:10.1038/srep39849 (2016).

815 67 Martinez-de-la-Torre, M., Pombal, M. A. & Puelles, L. Distal-less-like protein distribution in the larval
816 lamprey forebrain. *Neuroscience* **178**, 270-284, doi:10.1016/j.neuroscience.2010.12.030 (2011).

817 68 Sugahara, F., Murakami, Y., Pascual-Anaya, J. & Kuratani, S. Reconstructing the ancestral vertebrate
818 brain. *Dev Growth Differ* **59**, 163-174, doi:10.1111/dgd.12347 (2017).

819 69 Noro, M., Sugahara, F. & Kuraku, S. Reevaluating *Emx* gene phylogeny: homopolymeric amino acid
820 tracts as a potential factor obscuring orthology signals in cyclostome genes. *BMC Evol Biol* **15**, 78,
821 doi:10.1186/s12862-015-0351-z (2015).

822 70 Carrera, I., Ferreira-Galve, S., Sueiro, C., Anadon, R. & Rodriguez-Moldes, I. Tangentially migrating
823 GABAergic cells of subpallial origin invade massively the pallium in developing sharks. *Brain Res Bull*
824 **75**, 405-409, doi:10.1016/j.brainresbull.2007.10.013 (2008).

825 71 Garcia-Moreno, F. *et al.* Absence of Tangentially Migrating Glutamatergic Neurons in the Developing
826 Avian Brain. *Cell Rep* **22**, 96-109, doi:10.1016/j.celrep.2017.12.032 (2018).

827 72 Murakami, Y. *et al.* Identification and expression of the lamprey *Pax6* gene: evolutionary origin of the
828 segmented brain of vertebrates. *Development* **128**, 3521-3531 (2001).

829 73 Puelles, L. Thoughts on the development, structure and evolution of the mammalian and avian
830 telencephalic pallium. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci* **356**, 1583-1598, doi:10.1098/rstb.2001.0973
831 (2001).

832 74 Grillner, S. & Robertson, B. The Basal Ganglia Over 500 Million Years. *Curr Biol* **26**, R1088-R1100,
833 doi:10.1016/j.cub.2016.06.041 (2016).

834 75 Perez-Fernandez, J., Stephenson-Jones, M., Suryanarayana, S. M., Robertson, B. & Grillner, S.
835 Evolutionarily conserved organization of the dopaminergic system in lamprey: SNc/VTA afferent and
836 efferent connectivity and D2 receptor expression. *J Comp Neurol* **522**, 3775-3794,
837 doi:10.1002/cne.23639 (2014).

838 76 Stephenson-Jones, M., Floros, O., Robertson, B. & Grillner, S. Evolutionary conservation of the
839 habenular nuclei and their circuitry controlling the dopamine and 5-hydroxytryptophan (5-HT) systems.
840 *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **109**, E164-173, doi:10.1073/pnas.1119348109 (2012).

841 77 Stephenson-Jones, M., Kardamakis, A. A., Robertson, B. & Grillner, S. Independent circuits in the
842 basal ganglia for the evaluation and selection of actions. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **110**, E3670-3679,
843 doi:10.1073/pnas.1314815110 (2013).

844 78 Stephenson-Jones, M., Samuelsson, E., Ericsson, J., Robertson, B. & Grillner, S. Evolutionary
845 conservation of the basal ganglia as a common vertebrate mechanism for action selection. *Curr Biol* **21**,
846 1081-1091, doi:10.1016/j.cub.2011.05.001 (2011).
847

a

b

Retinotopy at three *levels* of visual processing

